

VEHICULAR ROAD TRAFFIC ACCIDENTS IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF MALASIQUI, PANGASINAN

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Abstract. Blindness is a huge challenge that causes many problems, such as a lack of social relationships, limited activities, and lack of employment. Existing solutions such as the white stick, assistive pets, and technologies that help blind people avoid obstacles are still in development. Unfortunately, not all blind people have a companion in life, and they face the struggles of life on their own. This study helps blind people recognize objects that they cannot see, distinguish people using face recognition, and help them move from one place to another, without assistance. The device is integrated with a GPS feature and has a mobile application where a family member can monitor or track the location can document, systematically analyze, and come up with new knowledge that will improve their classes and the outside world, this would be a huge blessing for these physically challenged people who would mostly be able to see the objects and people in front, travel to other places, and mostly detect obstacles that can harm them.

Keywords. Vehicular Road Traffic Accident, Road Safety Program, Attributes

1 Introduction

A Vehicular Road Traffic accident, also called a motor vehicle collision, car accident, or car crash, occurs when a vehicle collides with another vehicle, pedestrian, animal, road debris, or other stationary obstruction, such as a tree, pole, or building. Vehicular Road Traffic Accidents often result in injury, disability, death, and property damage as well as financial costs to both society and the individuals involved. Road transport is the most dangerous situation people deal with daily, but casualty figures from such incidents attract less media attention than other, less frequent types of tragedy (Grecia, 2020).

Not a day passes without RTA happening on the roads and countless people are victimized or disabled. Often members of the whole family are wiped out. Those who are affected or victimized are mostly people in their prime productive age. The highest burden of injuries and fatalities is borne disproportionately by poor people, as they are mostly pedestrians, cyclists, and passengers of buses and mini-busses. (J Family Med Prim Care, 2012)

Vehicular Road Traffic accidents are mainly caused by human mistakes such as inattention, misbehavior, and distraction. Many companies and institutes have proposed methods and techniques for the improvement of driving safety and the reduction of vehicular road traffic accidents. The commonly developed technologies for road and traffic perception include obstacle detection (vehicles, pedestrians, etc.) and road detection (road driving region, lane detection, road structure detection, etc.). (Advanced Driver Intention Inference, 2020)

Road traffic crashes result in the deaths of approximately 1.35 million people around the world each year and leave between 20 and 50 million people with non-fatal injuries. More than half of all road traffic deaths and injuries involve vulnerable road users, such as pedestrians, cyclists, and motorcyclists and their passengers.

The young are particularly vulnerable on the world's roads and road traffic injuries are the leading cause of death for children and young adults aged 5-29. Young males under 25 years are more likely to be involved in road traffic crashes than females, with 73% of all road traffic deaths occurring among young males of that age. Developing economies record higher rates of road traffic injuries, with 93% of fatalities coming from low- and middle-income countries.

In addition to the human suffering caused by road traffic injuries, they also incur a heavy economic burden on victims and their families, both through treatment costs for the injured and through loss of productivity of those killed or disabled.

More broadly, road traffic injuries have a serious impact on national economies, costing countries 3% of their annual gross domestic product. (WHO, 2016).

The Metropolitan Manila Development Authority (MMDA) has already released the full Metro Manila Accident Reporting and Analysis System (MMARAS) annual report for 2019, so it's time to see how much safer or more dangerous the roads in the metro have become over the past year. In 2018, a total of 116,906 incidents were reported, representing an increase of 6.25% from the year prior. In 2019, the total of reported incidents rose to 121,771, representing a year-on-year increase of 4.16%. On average, there were 334 reported accidents per day, with one resulting in a fatality, 56 being non-fatal, and 276 leading to damages to property. For the whole of 2019, 372 incidents with fatalities were tallied—down from 383 in the previous year. But as in 2018, there were still 394 recorded deaths from these incidents with fatalities. Meanwhile, there were 20,466 non-fatal accidents and 100,933 road mishaps that incurred damages to property (Grecia, 2020).

In Malasiqui, The Malasiqui police are reminding motorcycle riders to always wear standard protective helmets, as they strictly implement the national helmet law, which resulted in the apprehension of 34 motorcycle riders here on Thursday. They advise the public to wear protective helmets, which are standard with import commodity clearance stickers whenever traveling using motorcycles for their protection. In case of an accident, the helmet can protect them, whether they are a rider or a passenger, from further injury, Police Supt. Franklin Ortiz, chief of Malasiqui Police Station (MPS), said in an interview Friday.

Ortiz said they are strictly enforcing the helmet law to ensure the safety of motorcycle riders and their back riders. "We are applying the national law; however, we issued both the Land Transportation Office's temporary operator's permit (LTO-TOP) by deputized policemen and also the municipal traffic citation ticket (TCT)," he said.

From January to Nov. 23 this year, MPS recorded 41 injured motorcycle riders who were not wearing helmets, while one death was noted. He said the apprehended violators were penalized PHP1,500 for LTO-TOP tickets, or PHP40 for the municipal TCT. Ortiz also emphasized the importance of obeying all traffic laws to maintain order and security on the roads.

Abide with traffic laws not only on helmet law but all other laws about transportation and traffic rules and regulations. Let us be in sound body and mind when driving and let us be disciplined drivers, he added.

A total of 360 helmet law violators were apprehended by different police stations in the province, with the MPS having the highest number of apprehensions on Thursday alone based on the report of the Pangasinan Police Provincial Office – which was posted on its official Facebook page – on Friday. (Pasion, 2019)

The Land Transportation Office (LTO) Ilocos regional office is conducting road safety seminars targeting the young people in the region as part of its CARS (Creating Advocates for Road Safety) project of the agency. LTO-1 regional director, lawyer Teofilo Guadiz III, said the CARS project is a nationwide road safety advocacy of the LTO.

We are now more on the preventive side. There is a paradigm shift from (us being) apprehending officers to road safety advocates because our main thrust is to minimize road accidents or violence on the road, he said in an interview Thursday, Guadiz said that attendees to the road safety seminar, mostly young individuals, were given interactive lectures about traffic rules, traffic signs, and defensive driving.

We give them precautions on how to drive safely; the do's and don'ts in the hope of lessening road accidents. It's a one-day activity, wherein the morning is composed of lectures while the afternoon is for practical exercises. Guadiz added that the target of the seminar depends on the needs of the region. "It is an off-shoot of frequent road accidents. In Region 1, we noticed that the number of accidents among young people ages 18 to 29 increases significantly, especially motorcycle accidents," he said.

In 2018, out of the 11,331 road crashes in Region 1 recorded by the Philippine National Police, some 3,190 persons involved belonged to the 29-year-old and below age group, he added.

From August to October this year, out of the 787 road crashes, 655 persons involved belonged to the 29-year-old below age group," Guadiz said. He said most of the accidents or crashes happened every Friday and Saturday night. The involved persons were mostly under the influence of alcohol and those not wearing helmets. (Austria, 2019)

2 Review of Related Literature

In some places, traffic volume is consistently, extremely large, either during periods referred to as rush hour or perpetually. Exceptionally, traffic upstream of a vehicular collision or an obstruction, such as construction, may also be constrained, resulting in a traffic jam. Such dynamics of traffic congestion are known as traffic flow. Traffic engineers sometimes gauge the quality of traffic flow in terms of the level of service (Boris Kerner, 2017).

Traffic accidents may occur for several reasons. Some are unpredictable and not measurable or avoidable by the human being, for example as with climatic conditions. However, the man can take precautions that often are not taken into account (for example, non-circular on days of rain, wet pavement, or in areas of collapse or fall of stones).

Other causes have to do with the mere negligence and irresponsibility of drivers, as is the case of driving without a seat belt placed, unless the vehicle has the required technical verification, without sleep, alcohol, etc. All these situations increase the chances of some kind of accident that can generate human injury very severe (even death), as well as serious material losses. (Moser, 2014)

An accident is a violent event that occurs unintentionally, through the work of chance and that causes damage, without controlling it. Road traffic in many cases would have been prevented if preventive measures had been taken, and are only accidental by not being malicious but contracted by mere negligence. We can only call accident to very specific cases such as when a lightning strike may fall on a vehicle, or a tree by a very violent storm; looked at from the side of the pedestrian, that for example still on the sidewalk is run over by a vehicle, or when crossing while the traffic light was red; or if being conductive it atropellase a pedestrian who crossed without care and unexpectedly when it was not him.

They are generally found by mechanical failure of the vehicles, or oversights, such as driving distracted; or carelessness (talking by cell phone, drunken driving, carrying a child or a pet near or over, going to too much speed, etc.).

They include traffic accidents utilizing air, River, sea, and land, these being the most numerous by the higher number of vehicles who choose this way of transit, roads.

Those who cause an accident are liable to suffer legal consequences to being sued and sentenced in civil and/or criminal prosecution and may have to repair the damages in the first case or be punished with deprivation of liberty in the second, when for example as a result of the accident, someone lost his life (Wanlberg, 2012).

Every year, 1.25 million people die in road crashes – an alarming figure for what experts say is a preventable global health issue. In its 2015 report on road safety, the World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that 10,379 people died due to road crashes in 2013 – a figure higher than the 1,513 recorded in the Philippines' Department of Public Works and Highway-Traffic Accident Recording and Analysis System.

Various proposals have been raised to arrest the alarming number of road crashes, with lawmakers crafting proposals to improve road safety measures: from the need to rethink the design and construction of roads and keep them up to date with international standards, to implementing proper road safety education and training. Rappler lists down existing laws and policies on road safety in the Philippines, including proposed measures still pending in Congress.

Vehicular accidents cannot be avoided especially if the driver violates some traffic rules, such as reckless driving or, under the influence of alcohol or drugs. Accidents may probably happen at any time or anywhere along the way.

With the advent of science and technology, new and modernized traffic facilities are introduced. However, despite the modernizations, traffic congestion and accidents persist to exist. The only way to at least cope with the prevailing traffic-related problems is coordinated traffic management (Delizo, 2014). According to him, traffic management is designed to make the traffic way safer for travelers, tourists, businessmen, and visitors, expedite the movement of traffic, and provide convenience and comfort to the traffic facilities users. The major causes of traffic congestion are physical inadequacy which is characterized by a lack of roads; narrow bridges, railroad crossings, and lack of traffic facilities; poor control measures which are characterized by ineffective mechanical control devices, inefficient traffic officers, and poor implementation of traffic laws, rules, and regulations; human errors which are used by slow drivers or poor driving habits; pedestrian mistakes; traffic law enforcers' errors; poor planning by government officials including the PNP, poor

legislation by the legislators; and poor road maintenance due to unrepaired diggings, cracks on road pavements or unfinished road pavement concreting. These causes can be attributed to poor and inappropriate budgets for the maintenance and repair of the traffic facilities. On the other hand, the authors stated that the police should also report lights out, and damaged portions of traffic ways to expedite the action by concerned government offices.

In connection with the above-stated causes of traffic accidents, systematic and effective traffic management is needed (Boris Kerner, 2017). According to him, this includes all public surface facilities traversing and parking and all types of conveyances for the movement of persons and things, all agencies having responsibilities for ascertaining traffic flow requirements, planning, approving, funding, construction, and/or maintaining these public facilities for such movements and all agencies responsible for licensing, approving, restricting, stopping, prohibiting or controlling the use of these facilities.

According to Delizo (2014), for successful and effective traffic management and enforcement of laws and to reduce traffic-related problems such as congestion and car accidents, specific roles and responsibilities are vested in the Department of Transportation and Communication (DOTC) as the executive department of the national government which is the Land Transportation Office (LTO) and Land Transportation Franchising and Regulatory Board (LTFRB) are attached. They are responsible for the implementation of the Land Transportation Code of the Philippines (R.A. 4136) particularly on the issuance of driver's licenses, registration of motor vehicles, approval of franchises for public conveyances, and conducting safety traffic seminars. The other agency is the Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH), the main executive department of the national government which is responsible for the planning, construction, and maintenance of traffic particularly those categorized as national highways and other major road arteries; the legislative department which consists of the House of Senate and House of Representatives in the case of the national government and municipal or city councils (Sanguniang Bayan or Panglunsod in the local government) which are not only responsible for the passing or amendment of laws or ordinances concerning traffic laws but also they are involved in the planning, budgeting, and approval of government projects.

The Philippines National Police (PNP) composed of the traffic management group, the highway patrol group, and the police patrol (foot patrol and mobile patrol) are also responsible for the enforcement of traffic laws. They also performed other functions such as conducting information and dissemination campaigns, submitting traffic scheme proposals, and other functions as the need arose. (Investigative Hand-outs, 2011)

Academic institutions such as schools (public and private) are also responsible for basic traffic education by integrating into their respective curricular programs subjects or topics on traffic safety; the mass media networks (both print and broadcasting) that provide the necessary and updated traffic-related information to the public through their respective programs.

The community citizens, as a support group, can also help in the prevention of traffic congestion by assisting government offices in various activities, particularly during special occasions and holidays when traffic problem is likely to happen. (Delizo, 2014)

Other agencies such as the Public Information Office of some government agencies provide the necessary updated information to the public by creating traffic safety campaigns and other activities relating to traffic and the courts which are responsible for the adjudication of traffic-related cases filed before them.

Successful traffic management and law enforcement is not the sole responsibility of the government but rather a concerted effort between the public and private entities. (Delizo, 2014)

The standards for regulating movements on roads, streets, and highways are found in traffic laws, rules, and regulations (Cohen, 2016). These are special laws relative to traffic operation and traffic law enforcement but the basic laws regulating transportation in the Philippines today which are the legal basis of this study are Republic Act No. 4136 (Land Transportation and Traffic Code of the Philippines), Republic Act No. 8759 (Seat Belts Use Act of 1999), Republic Act No. 10586 (Anti-Drunk and Drugged of Driving Act of 2013) and Republic Act No. 10054 (Motorcycle Helmet Law).

In addition, traffic signs, pavement markings, and other control devices are traffic laws themselves. Violation of such constitutes a misdemeanor or infraction of the law. (Delizo, 2014).

In 2013, there was a decrease of 49,000 people injured by motorcycles, according to the US Department of Transportation (2014). While motorcycles decreased in fatalities overall, the number of people who died in alcohol-impaired driving decreased by 2.5%.

The list of countries by traffic-related death rate shows the annual number of road accident fatalities per capita per year and vehicle (Wikipedia, 2014). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), road traffic injuries caused an estimated 1.24 million, death worldwide in the year 2010 slightly down from 1.26 million people in 2000, That is, one person is killed every 025 seconds. Only 28 countries representing 448 million people (7% of the world's population) have adequate laws that address all the risk factors (speed, drunk-driving helmets, seatbelts, and child restraints). Over a third and road traffic deaths in low and middle-income countries are among pedestrians and cyclists. 8.7 per 100,000.

However, less than 35% of low-middle-income countries have policies in place to protect their road users. Middle-income countries have the highest annual road traffic fatality rates at 20.1 per 100,000 while the rate in high-income countries is lowest at 8.7 per 100,000.

Eighty percent of road traffic deaths occur in middle-income countries, which amounts to (72% of the world's population. Half of the world's road traffic death occurs among motorcyclists (23%) pedestrians (22%) and cyclists (5%) because they are vulnerable road users. Adults aged between 15 to 44 years account for 59% of global road traffic deaths 77% of road deaths are among men.

In the Philippines, according to Dante Lantin (assistant secretary of the Department of Transportation and Communication), road accident is the leading cause of death. Statistics from DOTC in 2014 reveals that 79% of road accident is caused by driver's error; 11% of road crash fatalities are caused by defective vehicle; 10% of road accident is caused by bad road conditions and ill-maintained roads; and 12% road accidents are caused by truck (2012).

The study noted that of all vehicle accidents to which the police were summoned, sleep-related vehicle accidents comprised 16% on major roads in Southwest England and over 20% on midland motorways. During the 24 hours, there were three major peaks at around 200, 600, and 1600. About half of their drivers were men under 30 years old; few such accidents involved women. The study concluded that sleep-related vehicle accidents are largely dependent on the time of day and account for a considerable proportion of vehicle accidents, especially those on motorways and other monotonous roads. As there are no norms for the United Kingdom's on-road use by age and sex and for the time of day within which to compare their data, the study findings are in close agreement with those from other countries.

The research paper of Mayou, Ehlers, and Bryan (2011) presents a 3-year follow of a prospective longitudinal study of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) after motor vehicle accidents. Participants composed of 546 patients were assessed when attending an emergency clinic shortly after a motor vehicle accident and 3 months and 1 year afterward. The study revealed that the prevalence of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) at years was 11%. Maintaining psychological factors, that is negative interpretation of intrusions, rumination, thought suppression, and anger cognition, were important in predicting the persistence of PTSD at 3 years, as were persistent health and financial problems after the accident. Other predictors were female sex, hospital admission for injuries perceived threat, and dissociation during the accident and litigation.

Depth, studies obtained from the internet concerning fatal vehicular accidents provide valuable data for implementing emergency services to reduce trauma-related mortality and strengthening legal measures in peak hours of fatal accidents. One study on this aspect was to determine fatal road traffic accident and their relationship with head injuries. This study involved post-mortem reports and clinical records of victims of road accidents autopsied from 2001 to 2005 at the Department of Forensic Medicine and Toxicology of India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi. The findings reveal that out of a total of 7008 medico-legal autopsies conducted during the study 2472 (35.27%) were vehicular accidents. The male/female ratio was 7:49:1 (the commonest age group affected was between 27-40 years involving 1341 (54.24%) cases. Pre-hospital mortality was in 985 (39.84% cases. Fatal traumatic brain injuries were seen in 1899 (68.73% cases and Skull fractures were found in 1183 (69.63% cause of road injury; the most common bone fracture was temporal bone (n=559), 47.25%). The commonest variety of intracranial hemorrhage was subdural hemorrhage (n=1514, 89.11%). The craniotomy was done in 297 (17.45%) cases; maximum mortality (41.07%) was seen within 4 days. The most commonly injured abdominal organ was the liver (n=532, 21.52%). No significant differences were evident in the incidence of fatal vehicular accidents on weekends and weekdays. However, November month took the maximum toll of death (n=273, 11.04%) of the total. Vehicular accident fatalities in five years duration 53.20% Of fatal accidents occurred between 6 pm to 6 am. The

results of the study emphasized the need to improve pre-hospital care with the provision of trauma services at the site and to establish neurosurgical facilities for trauma injuries.

In a research report published by the U.S. Department of Transportation in 2012, the estimated annual cost of traffic fatalities and injuries in the U.S. exceeds \$99 billion, according to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Several groups are particularly at risk for traffic accidents and fatalities. The research report stated that in 2011, there were 1,987 traffic deaths of drivers between 15 and 20 years old, while 5401 people 65 years old and older were killed in crashes. Motorcyclists accounted for 4612 fatalities in 2011. Personal Behavior as a role. The study also found motorcyclists or their passengers who died, 40% were not wearing helmets at the time of the crash. According to the CDC, 16% of traffic crash fatalities were vulnerable road users- pedestrians (4432), bicycles (667), and others (198).

In the Philippines, motorcycles had the highest number of fatalities in 2014 in road accidents, according to a research report published in 2014. The study added that a total of 20,515 motorcycles were involved in Metro Manila Road accidents in 2014, data based on the Metro Manila Accident Recording and Analysis Section of the MMDA. Of the figure, 204 were fatal. The report further said that of the 90,258 road accidents in the National Capital Region, 418 were fatal, 18,685 resulted in non-fatal injuries and 73,175 resulted in damage to property.

3 Research Design

This study uses descriptive research which aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation, or phenomenon. It can answer what, where, when, and how questions, but not why questions. The researcher is solely interested in describing the situation or case under my research study. It is a theory-based design method that is created by gathering, analyzing, and presenting collected data. This allows the researcher to provide insights into the why and how of research. Descriptive design helps others better understand the need for the research.

Malasiqui, officially the Municipality of Malasiqui (Pangasinan: Baley na Malasiqui; Ilocano: Illi ti Malasiqui; Tagalog: Bayan ng Malasiqui), is a 1st class municipality in the province of Pangasinan, Philippines. According to the 2015 census, it has a population of 130,275 people.

The Key Informants in this study are the Police Officers in both the Patrol and Traffic Section, the Police Investigation Section together with their Non-Uniformed Personnel which keeps all the records and data of vehicular road traffic accidents, and also the Auxiliary Groups consisting of Local Traffic Officers and POSO.

The data gathered in the Malasiqui Police Station about the characteristics of vehicular road traffic accidents; Number of vehicular accidents, Types of vehicular accident, Time of Occurrence of vehicular accidents and the vehicles involved together with the factors can be attributed to vehicular road traffic accidents consisting of man-made errors and mechanical defects were analyzed by the researcher through the use of percentage and ranking. After a thorough analysis, an interpretation of data was conducted to understand such a study.

4 Presentation and Analysis of Data

Table 1 shows the Statistical Data of Vehicular Road Traffic Accidents from the year 2016-2020, the Year 2019 has the most accidents with 295 recorded incidents because road users are very hard-headed in the sense that they are not obeying the traffic law and ordinances in the municipality, followed by the Year 2017 with 275 recorded incidents, the Year 2018 with 274 recorded incidents, the Year 2016 with 264 recorded incidents and lastly Year 2020 with only 49 recorded incidents. There is a very low number of recorded incidents in the year 2020 because this is the year wherein Lockdowns due to Pandemic of COVID 19 is present and also PNP is strictly implementing the OPLAN SITA to lessen the accidents in the municipality as stated in the conceptual literature.

Table 1. Characteristics of Vehicular Road Traffic Accidents as to Number of Accidents from the Year 2016-2020

Types of Accidents	Cases	Percentage	Ranking
Head-On	463	40%	1
Self-Accident	312	27%	2
Angle Impact	104	9%	3
Hit Pedestrian	69	6%	4
Hit Object	58	5%	5
Side Swipe	58	5%	5
Hit and Run	35	3%	6
Hit Parked Vehicles	35	3%	6
No Collision Stated	23	2%	7
Total	1,157	100%	N/A

Source: Malasiqui Police Station

The table below shows the types of vehicular accidents and the percentage in Malasiqui in the year 2016-2020. It is enumerated that the no. 1 nature/type of vehicular accident is Head-On with 40%. Perhaps the driver involved in this accident is not in focus while driving such as texting or sleepy or the driver is under the influence of drugs like liquor though they are prohibited. Self-Accident is the no.2 with 27% which is perhaps a fault of the drivers on the road, the no.3 is Angle Impact with 9%, followed by Hit Pedestrian with 6% wherein the driver hit the pedestrian and helps him/her at the same time. Another is hitting an object and Side Swipes are incurred with both 5% wherein according to the police records is due to the carelessness of drivers that's why it happened. Lastly, it was followed by Hit Parked Vehicles and Hit and Run with 3% because of distracted driving (using cellphones while driving) and No Collision Stated with 2%.

Table 2. Characteristics of Vehicular Road Traffic Accidents as to the Time of Occurrence of Accidents

Period of Occurrence	Total Accidents	Cases (2016-2020)	Percentage	Ranking
Afternoon Period (12:00NN- 5:59 PM)	1,157	555	48%	1
Evening Period (6:00 PM-11:59 PM)	1,157	405	35%	2
Morning Period (12:00MN- 11:59AM)	1,157	197	17%	3

Source: Malasiqui Police Station

Shows in Table 3 that the Afternoon period has 555 Cases which is equivalent to 48% reigning in the Number 1 Rank reason that this time, more drivers were distracted because of too many people on the road, followed by the Evening Period having 405 Cases which is equivalent to 35% in Rank 2 in the Period of Occurrence because this is the time wherein rush hour in going home from work or school is present and also for the reason that claimed of having poor eyesight and also drunk driving in accordance to my conceptual literature. Morning Period is in Rank 3 with 197 cases which is equivalent to 17% because, although there is a rush hour in going to work or school, police officers and traffic officers are well alert and active at this time that's why they can still manage and control vehicles in the road and workers and students do not have the same time in going to work or school, they do have different time schedules while in going home, most of the time, they do have the same schedule.

Table 3. Characteristics of Vehicular Road Traffic Accidents as to Vehicles Involved.

Vehicles Involved	Cases	Percentage	Ranking
Motorcycles	763	42%	1
Private Cars	345	19%	2
Service Utility Vehicles	291	16%	3
Public Utility Vehicles	163	9%	4
Public Buses	109	6%	5
Bicycles	91	5%	6
Others	55	3%	7
Total	1,817	100%	N/A

Source: Malasiqui Police Station

Table 4, shows that the Rank 1 in Vehicles involved in an accident is Motorcycles because, according to Malasiqui Police Station, most of the people in the Municipality can only afford to buy motorcycles and even children aged 15 years old and below can learn how to drive motorcycles that's why in the records of MPS, Motorcycles is the mostly used in an accident, followed by Private cars with 220 cases (19%), SUV with 185 cases (16%), PUV with 104 cases (9%), Public Buses with 69 cases (6%) and Bicycles with 58 cases (5%). Others in the tables represent other types of vehicles like Kuliglig, experimented vehicles, etc., with 35 cases (3%) recorded cases. The reason for these accidents also is because of drunk driving, poor eyesight, lack of discipline on the road, and mechanical defects.

Table 5. Factors can be attributed to Vehicular Road Traffic Accidents Concerning Man-Made Errors

Causes of Vehicular Road Traffic Accidents (Man-Made Errors)	Cases	Percentage	Ranking
Reckless Driving/Driver	544	47%	1
Lack of Discipline while driving such as drunk and texting while driving	370	32%	2
Unable to follow rules and regulations	185	16%	3
Human factors such as Lack of Perception and Poor Eyesight	58	5%	4
Total	1,157	100%	N/A

Source: Malasiqui Police Station

In the Municipality of Malasiqui, reckless driving having 544 Cases (47%) is a major moving traffic violation. It is usually a more serious offense than careless driving, improper driving, or driving without due care and attention and is often punishable by fines, imprisonment, and/or driver's suspension or revocation. Reckless driving is often defined as a mental state in which the driver displays a wanton disregard for the rules of the road; the driver often misjudges common driving procedures, causing accidents and other damages. Reckless driving has been studied by psychologists who found that reckless drivers score high in risk-taking personality traits. However, no one cause can be assigned to this state. There are some Municipalities in the Pangasinan such as Malasiqui, where mental state is not considered but rather a set of more than a dozen specific violations can be deemed reckless. Excessive speed by itself is sufficient for a reckless driving conviction in some jurisdictions.

Lack of discipline while driving example under the influence of drugs or texting while driving is no.2 having 370 Cases (32%). Some may argue that talking on a cell phone while driving is no different than conversing with a passenger in your car. However, research (Drews, Pasupathi, and Strayer, 2012) suggests otherwise. Passengers share the same context. Conversation flows more or less with the demands placed on the driver. Passengers can make the driver aware of any road conditions or can suspend conversation when driving conditions intensify. We are also more likely to tell passengers to wait or hold on if we need to divert our mental energy to driving. The person on the other end of a cell phone conversation or text lacks this context and is less likely to be told to wait.

Unable to follow Traffic rules and regulations is in the third rank with 185 Cases (16%). There are good cops and there are bad cops. But whatever the situation, it's always best if you know the law. Having a little more knowledge of traffic rules and penalties goes a long way when it comes to driving in the Philippines. For once in your driving life, you're sure to have been surprised by an apprehending traffic officer or policeman with a violation you haven't heard of. As they say, ignorance does not excuse you from the long arm of the law. Knowing the violations and penalties just might save you time and money.

Human factors such as lack of perception and poor eyesight are the last causes of the accident with 58 Cases (5%). Traffic safety requires that drivers of automobiles, buses, and trucks can able to accurately and instantly judge distances that are ahead, to the rear, and to the sides. Failure to do so can lead to accidents. It is well established that people with good vision in both eyes can judge distance accurately using their stereoscopic binocular vision.

Table 6. Factors can be attributed to Vehicular Road Traffic Accidents
 Concerning Mechanical Defects

Causes of Vehicular Road Traffic Accidents (Mechanical Defects)	Cases	Percentage	Ranking
Faulty Brakes	382	33%	1
Tire Blows Out	312	27%	2
Faulty Head-lights and Tail-lights	232	20%	3
Faulty Steering and Suspensions	162	14%	4
Malfunctioning Wipers and Clutch	69	6%	5
Total	1,157	100%	N/A

Source: Malasiqui Police Station

Faulty Brakes (Rank 1 with 382 Cases equivalent to 33%)

Brake failure is one of the common mechanical defects that can lead to automobile accidents. Modern automobile technologies, such as dual brake systems, reduce the risk of mechanical failure. In case of a circuit failure, the other circuit will come into action and enable the car to brake. Another technology that has made cars safer is the anti-lock braking system that prevents the front car wheels from locking in case of an emergency.

Tire Blow Outs (Rank 2 with 312 Cases equivalent to 27%)

Tires are much safer today than they were a few years ago. However, worn-out tires and under-inflated tires are major causes of motor vehicle accidents. Faulty suspensions and improperly aligned suspensions may result in uneven tires and ultimately lead to an accident.

Faulty Steering Systems and Suspensions (Rank 4 with 162 Cases equivalent to 14%)

If a car is traveling at a high speed and the suspension system malfunctions, it can cause a major accident no matter how experienced the driver is. To prevent accidents caused by mechanical failures, the driver needs to take preventive steps. Drivers should maintain their vehicles well and have the equipment and components tested by trained personnel at regular intervals.

Faulty Headlights and Taillights (Rank 3 with 232 cases equivalent to 20%)

A large percentage of car accidents occur at night compared to the daytime, because of low visibility when drivers must depend on lights to be able to see. If the car has broken or dim headlights, brake lights, or taillights, then it can become extremely difficult for the motorist to see and for the other drivers to spot them. Inspect all lights regularly to make sure they are in perfect working order.

Malfunctioning Wipers and Clutch (Rank 5 with 69 cases equivalent to 6%)

Driving in rain and snow can be extremely difficult and you need good quality and properly functioning wipers for safe driving. If the car's wipers malfunction when you are driving in a snowstorm or rain, you will immediately lose visibility.

5 Results, Conclusion, and Recommendation

The recorded number of vehicular road traffic accidents in the Municipality of Malasiqui, Pangasinan for the past (5) five years (2016-2020) were still increasing except the year 2020. The recorded incidents in the year 2020 are too low because this is the year wherein Lockdowns due to the pandemic of Covid 19 are present and PNP is strictly implementing the OPLAN SITA.

The types of accident consist of Head-on, Self-accident, Angle Impact, Hit Pedestrian, Hit object, Side swipe, Hit and run, Hit parked vehicles and no collision stated transpired because of the following reasons: the driver was not focused, drunk driving, and distracted driving, sleepy, carelessness and lack of respect to the laws and regulations.

The afternoon Period has the highest number of recorded incidents for the reason that this is the time wherein rush hour in going home from work or school is present and the Evening period has the 2nd highest incidents for the reason claimed of having poor eyesight, drunk driving and lack of respect of laws and regulations is present. The morning Period was the lowest recorded incident because police and traffic law enforcers are still active at this time.

Motorcycles are the most vehicles involved in an accident in the Municipality of Malasiqui because most of the person can only afford to buy motorcycles and considering their age, even children aged 15 years old and below can learn how to drive motorcycles but still lack training, education, and experience. Private cars, SUVs, PUVs, Public buses, Bicycles, and experiment vehicles also belong to the criteria of this accident because of still in Drunk driving, Poor eyesight, Lack of discipline on the road, and also because of Man-made errors, and Mechanical defects.

The Proposed Comprehensive Road Safety Program can be tried out; reproduced in several copies for distribution to the police, traffic enforcers of Malasiqui, PNP officials of the PNP Provincial Office, Highway Patrol Group, and the LTO and likewise be tried out.

Educate more road users to be law-abiding citizens, conduct seminars to all riders and even pedestrians about the Laws and penalties if they don't obey them, and also always conduct road inspections and provide solutions to the problems that will be seen in the said road inspections.

A parallel study or follow-up study is recommended especially after a year or two in the implementation of the proposed road safety program, if it is effective then continue to obey and apply it but if it is still the same, then improve more about road safety program to ensure the accident-free Malasiqui, Pangasinan.

References

- Advanced Driver Intention Inference. 2020. "An Ensemble Deep Learning Approach for Driver Lane Change Intention Inference". Austria, Hilda, 2019. LTO Promotes Road Safety in Ilocos Region. Philippine News Agency
- Boris, Kerner S. 2017. "Introduction to Modern Traffic Flow Theory and Control: The Long Road to Three-Phase Traffic Theory."
- Cohen, Simon. 2016 "Traffic Safety Management: Volume 4".
- Delizo, Bernardo G., 2014. "Traffic Management and Accident Investigation: Second Edition 2014".
- Grecia, Leandre. 2020. MMDA reports an all-time high of 121,771 road accidents in 2019. TopGear Philippines
- J Family Med Prime. 2012. "A Public Health Perspective of Road Traffic Accidents".
- Moser, Andreas. 2014. "Handbook of Accident Reconstruction: Vehicle Dynamics".
- Pasion, Ahikam, 2019. Road Crashes in Pangasinan Down by 27.94%. Philippine News Agency.
- World Health Organization, 2016. "Global Status Report on Road Safety 2016" World Health Organization Report.